

Agro2Circular

D1.6 – EFSA agrifood pre-dossier & compliance with food standards

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Table of contents

1	List of abbreviations	7
2	Executive summary <abstract>	8
3	Introduction	10
4	Requirements	12
4.1	Identity of the NF	12
4.2	Production process	13
4.3	Compositional data	15
4.3.1	Stability	18
4.3.1.1	Stability of the bulk material	18
4.3.1.2	Stability when added to food formulations	19
4.4	Specifications	19
4.5	Other aspects to be included	20
5	Conclusions	21
6	Evaluation of the results	22
7	Bibliography	23
8	ANNEX I - EFSA Novel Food Pre-Dossier Template	24

List of Tables

Table 1.	Analysis of phenolic and fibre extracts obtained from lemon waste, on average.	15
Table 2.	Analysis of phenolic and fibre extracts obtained from artichoke waste, on average.	16
Table 3.	Analysis of phenolic and fibre extracts obtained from broccoli waste, on average.	16
Table 4.	Analysis of phenolic extracts obtained from grape waste, on average.	17

Table 5. Analysis of fibre extracts obtained from apple waste, on average.	17
Table 6. Analysis of other compounds of interest in phenolic extracts.	18
Table 7. Analysis of other compounds of interest in phenolic extracts.	18
Table 8. Specification of the NF	19
Table 9. Structure and Content of the EFSA Novel Food Pre-Dossier Template	24

List of Figures

Figure 1. Diagram for obtaining NF from agri-food waste	13
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1 List of abbreviations

ADME → Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion

AOAC → Association of Official Agricultural Chemists

EC → European Commission

EFSA → European Food Safety Authority

EU → European Union

HPLC → High-Performance Liquid Chromatography

HPLC-MS/MS → High-Performance Liquid Chromatography–Tandem Mass Spectrometry

ICP-MS → Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry

ISO → International Organization for Standardization

NDA → Novel Foods and Food Allergens

NF → Novel Food

RH → Relative humidity

WP → Work Package

2 Executive summary <abstract>

This document provides guidance to applicants preparing applications for a new authorisation of novel foods in the European Union within the scope of Article 10 of Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 and Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/2469.

The present pre-dossier includes the information to be provided for an application submitted for the authorisation of a novel food, considering extracts obtained from agri-food waste used for the development of new food formulations (WP2 at laboratory scale and further scaling up in WP4) as novel foods, in terms of risks assessment.

In developing this document, consideration has been given to the "*Administrative guidance for the preparation of applications on novel foods pursuant to Article 10 of Regulation (EU) 2015/2283*"¹ as a general reference guide, as well as "*Safety of bovine milk osteopontin as a Novel food pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2015/2283*"² and "*Safety of water lentil protein concentrate from a mixture of Lemna gibba and Lemna minor as a novel food pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2015/2283*"³ as practical examples, among others.

The above Administrative guidance applies to all applications submitted to the European Commission from 27 March 2021 and should be used for the preparation of applications to be submitted from that date.

According to the guidance, the life-cycle of an application encompasses various steps and activities:

- Pre-submission phase: this covers the preparation of the application and all pre-submission activities;
- Submission phase and suitability check: consists of the application to the European Commission, and EFSA checks that the application is complete and suitable;
- Risk assessment phase: following the validation of the application, EFSA performs the risk assessment leading to the adoption of EFSA's scientific opinion by the EFSA Panel on Nutrition, Novel Foods and Food Allergens (NDA);

¹ <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-6488>

² <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7137>

³ <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7903>

- Post-adoption phase: EFSA's scientific opinion is published in the EFSA Journal and the EC prepares, where appropriate, a draft implementing act authorising the placing on the EU market of the novel food.

The present pre-dossier will improve the understanding of the application requirements after the application preparation and submission stage (pre-submission phase and submission phase), namely once the application has been validated and the documentation for the risk assessment phase has to be prepared.

3 Introduction

For the development of this document, it has been considered that the request for an application to place extracts of phenolic compounds and/or fibres from agri-food waste on the market as novel food (NF) has been validated by the EFSA in accordance with Article 10 of Regulation (EU) No 2015/2283.

The novel food is proposed for use in several food categories and is intended for the general population.

In accordance with Article 10(3) of Regulation (EU) 2015/2283, this document responds to the request for a scientific opinion on the extracts submitted by the European Commission to the European Food Safety Authority.

The aim of this pre-dossier is to gather as much information as possible to assess the safety of the extracts obtained in the project.

For this purpose, the requirements to be taken into account in Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 are considered.

It is expected that when assessing the safety of novel foods, the Authority will be able to decide whether:

- (a)** the novel food is as safe as a food of a comparable food category already on the Union market;
- (b)** the composition of the novel food and its conditions of use do not pose a risk to human health within the European Union;
- (c)** the novel food which is intended to replace another food does not differ from that food in such a way that its normal consumption would be nutritionally disadvantageous for consumers.

This document is structured in two main sections: a guidance part and an evaluation part. The guidance part (Sections 4 to 6) describes the regulatory framework and specific requirements for EFSA novel food applications, serving as a reference for applicants. The evaluation part (Section 7) reflects on the relevance and completeness of the information compiled in this project in light of these requirements. Together, they support both the

internal assessment of the project outcomes and future regulatory submissions. An annexed pre-dossier template has also been included to help align future documentation with EFSA expectations.

4 Requirements

Administrative and scientific requirements for NF applications referred to in Article 10 of Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 are listed in the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/24691 (Article 7).

In accordance with Article 7, the following information must be included:

- (a) The identity of the novel food;
- (b) the assessment of the production process;
- (c) compositional data;
- (d) specifications;
- (e) the history of use of the novel food and/or its source;
- (f) the proposed uses and use levels and anticipated intake;
- (g) absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME);
- (h) nutritional information;
- (i) toxicological information;
- (j) allergenicity;
- (k) an overall risk assessment for the novel food under the proposed uses and use levels and highlighting uncertainties and limitations where relevant;

The information collected and generated in work packages (WP) 1, 2 and 4 will be considered for this purpose.

4.1 Identity of the NF

NF are extracts of phenolic compounds or fibre extracts obtained from lemon peelings, broccoli peelings, apple peelings, cauliflower peelings, artichoke peelings or grape peelings.

These residues are generated by farms (which generate the residues during harvesting and commercial distribution of crops, as is the case for broccoli, cauliflower and artichoke residues), or by food and beverage processing and transformation companies (as is the case for lemon residues, apple residues, artichoke residues and grape residues). These crops have a high production rate in the south of Spain as well as in other European regions. The generation, collection, transport and storage of waste is carried out under appropriate

hygienic and sanitary conditions that prevent the spoilage of the raw material and its contamination (as described in deliverable D1.4). The waste, once delivered to the processing company to obtain phenolic compound extracts and/or fibre extracts, is analysed and characterised to ensure that it meets the appropriate standards for its recovery (according to task T1.4.3).

The results of the characterisation of these raw materials can be found in deliverable D1.3.

4.2 Production process

Waste is collected, transported and stored according to good management and handling practices included in D1.4 (Residues management plan).

The waste is processed on the basis of two different extraction routes. Route 1, carried out by CTNC and route 2 carried out by DMC.

In both routes, the waste is processed in pilot plants that include pre-treatment stages, extraction stage, separation and purification, and stabilisation of extracts, as shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Diagram for obtaining NF from agri-food waste

The different types of waste are processed separately, with no mixing of different raw materials.

The pre-treatment stages correspond to initial stages of physical/mechanical treatments of grinding or cutting to reduce the particle size and favour the extraction stage, homogenising the whole waste and maximising the plant surface area that will come into contact with the extractant solution.

For route 1 (detailed in deliverable D4.2), the extraction stage corresponds to an enzymatic extraction in liquid state, using a residue: enzyme solution ratio of 1:3. For this, osmotised water with an enzyme concentration of 0.01% (in relation to the solid fraction) is used, and the treatment is carried out at 25°C for 1h under stirring. After the extraction time, the temperature is increased to achieve enzyme inactivation.

As a result of the extraction stage, two fractions are obtained, one liquid and one solid. The fractions are separated mechanically by sieving filtration.

The liquid phase, rich in phenolic compounds, is subjected to a separation process by membrane filtration and subsequent purification using adsorption-desorption processes using high affinity resins. The purified phenolic extract is then subjected to a dehydration treatment by freeze-drying, which stabilises the extract.

The solid phase, rich in fibre, is subjected to a purification stage by washing with oxidising agent and subsequent washing with osmotised water to remove the oxidising agent. The purified fibre extract is then subjected to a dehydration treatment by drying in a climatic chamber, which stabilises the extract.

For route 2 (detailed in deliverable D4.3), a liquid phase enzyme extraction is carried out at a waste: enzyme solution ratio (using an enzyme dose of 1.5 ml of enzyme solution per kilogram of solid waste) of 1:3 at 50°C for 3 hours under stirring.

As a result of the extraction stage, two fractions are obtained, one liquid and one solid. The fractions are separated mechanically by sieving filtration. The liquid phase is subjected to a separation step by ultrafiltration to obtain soluble fibre on the one hand and phenolic compounds on the other hand.

The solid phase is then subjected to a microwave-assisted hydroalcoholic extraction. After extraction the liquid phase is mixed with the liquid phase obtained after ultra-filtration. The solid phase is intended to be used as a nutrient source in fermentations to be carried out in WP5.

The mixture of the solution rich in phenolic compounds is purified by adsorption-desorption treatments using high affinity resins.

The soluble fibre extract underwent an oven dehydration stabilisation process.

The purified phenolic compound extract undergoes a stabilisation process by freeze-drying and some of them are susceptible to be encapsulated in alginate spheres.

4.3 Compositional data

To confirm that the extraction process is reproducible and suitable to produce on a commercial scale a product with the required characteristics, NF composition data were provided for several independently produced batches.

For the development of this pre-dossier, the extracts obtained in route 1 have been considered.

The following tables show the nutritional composition of each extract and the analytical method used. The official analysis methods of the Association of Official Agricultural Chemists (AOAC) have been followed, which include analysis methods according to analytical parameter and food category.

Table 1. Analysis of phenolic and fibre extracts obtained from lemon waste, on average.

Parameter (%)	Phenolic extract	Fibre extract	Method of analysis
Moisture	4.1	5.1	Gravimetry
Carbohydrates (including sugars)	69.6	3.7	Calculation
Dietary fibre	20.8	74.6	Gravimetry
Proteins	3.7	7.9	Kjeldahl Gunning-Arnold (KGA)
Fat	0.1	6.0	Liquid-liquid extraction - Gravimetry
Ash	1.7	2.7	Gravimetry
Total sugar	18.4	1.7	Ion exchange HPLC

Table 2. Analysis of phenolic and fibre extracts obtained from artichoke waste, on average.

Parameter (%)	Phenolic extract	Fibre extract	Method of analysis
Moisture	4.2	6.3	Gravimetry
Carbohydrates (including sugars)	43.3	1.9	Calculation
Dietary fibre	33.4	75.1	Gravimetry
Proteins	15.8	10.7	Kjeldahl Gunning-Arnold (KGA)
Fat	0.3	1.9	Liquid-liquid extraction - Gravimetry
Ash	3.0	4.1	Gravimetry
Total sugar	13.2	0.8	Ion exchange HPLC

Table 3. Analysis of phenolic and fibre extracts obtained from broccoli waste, on average.

Parameter (%)	Phenolic extract	Fibre extract	Method of analysis
Moisture	4.8	5.4	Gravimetry
Carbohydrates (including sugars)	45.5	3.5	Calculation
Dietary fibre	6.1	70.1	Gravimetry
Proteins	18.9	10.8	Kjeldahl Gunning-Arnold (KGA)
Fat	1.2	0.4	Liquid-liquid extraction - Gravimetry
Ash	23.5	9.8	Gravimetry
Total sugar	38.7	<0,1	Ion exchange HPLC

Table 4. Analysis of phenolic extracts obtained from grape waste, on average.

Parameter (%)	Phenolic extract	Method of analysis
Moisture	8.9	Gravimetry
Carbohydrates (including sugars)	86.1	Calculation
Dietary fibre	0.6	Gravimetry
Proteins	1.3	Kjeldahl Gunning-Arnold (KGA)
Fat	0.1	Liquid-liquid extraction - Gravimetry
Ash	3.0	Gravimetry
Total sugar	55.2	Ion exchange HPLC

Table 5. Analysis of fibre extracts obtained from apple waste, on average.

Parameter (%)	Fibre extract	Method of analysis
Moisture	2.2	Gravimetry
Carbohydrates (including sugars)	9.9	Calculation
Dietary fibre	69.8	Gravimetry
Proteins	5.6	Kjeldahl Gunning-Arnold (KGA)
Fat	11.6	Liquid-liquid extraction - Gravimetry
Ash	0.9	Gravimetry
Total sugar	7.0	Ion exchange HPLC

Heavy metal content (ICP-MS method of analysis), pesticides (HPLC-MS/MS), and pathogenic microorganisms (Mesophilic aerobes (ISO 4833-2:2014), *Salmonella* (ISO 6579-1:2017), *L. monocytogenes* (ISO 11290-1:2017), moulds and yeasts (ISO 21527-2:2008) and *E. coli* β -Glucuronidase positive (ISO 16649-2:2001) have also been evaluated.

Salmonella and *L. monocytogenes* were not detected in any of the extracts analysed. Aerobic counts, mould and yeast counts and *E. coli* counts were <10 cfu/g in all extracts analysed (considering cfu as colony forming units).

As for other compounds of interest, total polyphenols, among other compounds, have been analysed in phenolic extracts.

Table 6. Analysis of other compounds of interest in phenolic extracts.

Parameter (mg/kg dry matter)	Lemon phenolic extract	Grape phenolic extract	Method of analysis
Total polyphenols	124,400	208,900	Folin–Ciocalteu
Hesperidin	52,796	-	HPLC
Limonin	10,763	-	HPLC
Vitamin C	641.1		HPLC

Table 7. Analysis of other compounds of interest in phenolic extracts.

Parameter (mg/kg dry matter)	Artichoke phenolic extract	Broccoli phenolic extract	Method of analysis
Total polyphenols	202.438	15,830	Folin–Ciocalteu
Chlorogenic acid	113,827	80.2	HPLC

4.3.1 Stability

4.3.1.1 Stability of the bulk material

The applicant performed stability testing with four independently produced batches of the NF under standard storage conditions. The tests were carried out at 25°C in dark sealed packages at 40–60% RH for a period of 6 months. The batches were analysed for microbiological stability and lipid oxidation over this period. Antioxidant capacity was also assessed over time.

These studies showed no significant changes in any of the microbiological parameters tested after 1, 1.5 and 6 months.

4.3.1.2 Stability when added to food formulations

Food formulations have been developed with the NFs described above:

- Juices with 1.5% fibre (from the various fibre extracts).
- Vegan burger with 1 to 2% fibre (from the different fibre extracts).
- Vegetable desserts with 0.3% fibre (from the different fibre extracts).
- Jams with 1% fibre (from the different fibre extracts)
- Juices with 0.5% phenolic compounds (from the different phenolic extracts)
- Compote with 0.5% phenolic compounds (from the different phenolic extracts).

Stability studies on food formulations are being carried out comparatively between samples including NF and control samples (without NF). Samples with NF and control without NF will be stored at room temperature (25°C) and 60% relative humidity, and under accelerated conditions (40°C and 75% relative humidity) for a maximum of 180 days.

During the study, a complete nutritional analysis of the formulations and microbiological quality shall be evaluated at 30-day intervals.

** The stability study is in its early stages, so there is no complete information available on the stability of the formulations compared to the control.*

4.4 Specifications

The specifications of the NF are indicated in **Table 8**:

Table 8. Specification of the NF

Parameter (unit)	Fibre/Phenolic extract
Fibre (%) ¹	70-80
Total polyphenols (%) ²	> 7
Moisture (%)	<9.0
Heavy metals (mg/kg)	
Arsenic	<0.1
Cadmium	<0.05
Lead	<0.05

Mercury	<0.05
Pesticides (mg/kg)	<0,01
Microbiological contaminants	
Mould/ yeast (cfu/g)	<10
Salmonella	Absent/ 25 g
L. monocytogenes	Absent/ 25 g
E. coli (cfu/g)	<10

¹ Applicable to fibre extracts

² Applicable to phenolic extracts

4.5 Other aspects to be included

Other aspects to be included in the safety assessment application are the history of use of the NF and/or its source.

It is also important to include a section on the proposed uses of NF and use levels and anticipated intake. This section should include the target population (e.g. in this case the general population, as NF is used as a food ingredient in several food categories). The target population is limited to adults only for the intake of NF as a food supplement.

The use levels will be specified per food category.

For anticipated intake, daily intake data for the food categories shall be considered, calculating the intake of the NF based on the uses proposed by the applicant and the proposed maximum use levels.

It is also important to provide information on absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME). The applicant shall provide data on digestion and bioavailability of NF, among others. This part could be based on previous studies already published about similar extracts.

Finally, toxicological information will be included, considering genotoxicity, subchronic toxicity or allergenicity, among others.

5 Conclusions

The preparation of this pre-dossier in the context of the safety assessment of NF (fibre extracts and phenolic extracts) is a strategic step that aims, in the first place, to highlight the quality of the products obtained in this project.

It is imperative to ensure that the extracts obtained, which are expected to be used in food (as well as in other sectors that are not of concern to us in this case, such as cosmetics), meet the necessary quality and safety standards.

This pre-dossier also plays a crucial role in understanding the process of requesting approval for a novel food. By outlining the specific requirements set out in Article 10 of Regulation (EU) 2015/2283, the document acts as a guide that facilitates navigation through the complexities of the regulatory framework, helping future applicants to understand EFSA's expectations.

The information available so far on A2C extracts allows the safety of these extracts to be assured, taking into account that relevant toxicological studies need to be carried out to complete the risk assessment.

6 Evaluation of the results

In light of one of the key objectives of the project, incorporating the extracted compounds into food formulations and pursuing future commercialization, it is essential to thoroughly understand the current regulations in the European Union that the developed products must comply with.

It is important to note that the preparation of a pre-dossier for EFSA contributes to strengthening consumer confidence in novel foods. This is essential considering the source of the NF in question: agri-food waste. By demonstrating the developers' commitment to safety and quality, an environment of transparency is fostered that can be beneficial for the acceptance of these products on the market, thereby promoting the circular economy.

Although conducting an EFSA novel food acceptance process may seem challenging due to the long timelines and the amount of information and analysis required, approval of a novel food is essential to market the product in the European Union and given the size and influence of the European market, obtaining approval can open significant doors for the marketing and distribution of the food.

7 Bibliography

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8 ANNEX I - EFSA Novel Food Pre-Dossier Template

This annex provides a structured template summarising all required sections for preparing a novel food pre-dossier in line with Article 10 of Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 and Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/2469.

Table 9. Structure and Content of the EFSA Novel Food Pre-Dossier Template

Section title	Content to include
1. Identity of the Novel Food	Source, botanical origin, physical form, intended use, processing level.
2. Production Process	Description of processing steps, control points, and standard operating procedures.
3. Compositional Data	Analytical composition (macro and micronutrients, contaminants), batch analysis, method of analysis.
4. Specifications	Chemical and microbiological limits; ranges and tolerances.
5. History of Use	Prior use of the food or its source in the EU or third countries.
6. Proposed Uses, Use Levels & Anticipated Intake	Target population, food categories, estimated daily intakes.
7. ADME (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion)	Data on digestion, metabolism, and bioavailability.
8. Nutritional Information	Impact on nutritional quality of diet.
9. Toxicological Information	Genotoxicity, subchronic toxicity, allergenicity, human studies.
10. Allergenicity	Potential allergenic reactions, comparison with known allergens.
11. Overall Risk Assessment	Summary of safety conclusions, uncertainties, and data gaps.

